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AUGMENTING LEARNERS' PERFORMANCE THROUGH INSTRUCTIONAL SUPPORT

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Abstract: This research was designed to assess the identified supports that elevate learner's performance under the new normal of education during the school year 2020-2021 as basis for strategic plan. The researchers used the descriptive research method to gather information about the respondents' demographic profile. The data obtained were analyzed using weighted mean on the identified supports. Based on the findings, teachers and parents should work together to effectively support the learner's wellbeing and development while on modular learning and in ensuring that the learners were doing their tasks and activities on time through constant communications and follow ups. Further, the flexible learning modality that the school chooses challenged the teachers to design activities that are good to the mental health of the students and the materials needed are locally available in their home. By recognizing the impact of this results, it is very important to provide appropriate support to the learners. Thus, the results suggested that there is still a need to elevate the support of the teachers and parents to provide quality learning. It can also be observed that despite covid-19 pandemic and new set-up of education, learners were still motivated to acquire quality learning.

Keywords: Learners Performance, Learners need, Instructional Support, Performance

1. Introduction

As we witness the Covid19 outbreak unfolding globally, more or less billion of students worldwide are unable to go to school or university, due to measures to stop the spread of COVID-19. Educators and educational system pay more attention and offer systematic support to vulnerable and shift our philosophy in teaching to a wider perspective that caters the needs of students.

Moreover, this pandemic is giving technology massive insights at scale as to what human development and learning looks like, allowing it to potentially shift from just content dissemination to augmenting relationships with teachers, personalization, and independence (Anderson, 2020). Large-scale, national efforts to utilize technology in

support of remote learning, distance education and online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic are emerging and evolving quickly (World Bank, 2020). Hence, the impact of corona virus makes us educators and the students rely more on the technology.

Many major countries have urged to make interventions. Educ.ar is the educational portal of the MOE of Argentina aimed at providing curate digital resources for teachers, administrators, students, and families. The program “Seguimos Educando”, developed by the MOE and the Secretariat of Media and Public Communication, began broadcasting educational content from April 1, 2020. Seguimos Educando airs 14 hours a day of television content and 7 hours a day of radio content specially produced for students as a result of school closures. For both radio and television, each lesson broadcast will have the presence of a teacher and a conductor (journalist, artist, scientist), in addition to the dissemination of teaching materials (Ministry of Education, 2020).

Moreover, as the world becomes increasingly interconnected, so do the risks we face. The COVID-19 pandemic has not stopped at national borders; it has also affected people regardless of nationality, level of education, income or gender. But the same has not been true for its consequences, which have hit the most vulnerable hardest (Schleicher, 2020). As of March 2020, COVID-19 has become a global pandemic, which has resulted in a maelstrom across the globe, bringing the world to a standstill (WHO, 2020). In consequence, various social and physical distancing measures have been introduced by the authorities including: lockdowns of non-essential businesses, closings of schools, universities, and bans on travel, cultural and sporting events as well as social gatherings (UNPB, 2020; Parnel et al., 2020).

UNESCO (2020) stated that these nationwide closures are impacting hundreds of millions of students. Several other countries have implemented localized closures impacting millions of additional learners. UNESCO is supporting countries in their efforts to mitigate the immediate impact of school closures, particularly for more vulnerable and disadvantaged communities, and to facilitate the continuity of education for all through remote learning. Similarly, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2020) indicated that school closures due to the COVID-19 outbreak have disrupted the education of at least 290.5 million students worldwide, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (as cited by McCarty (2020)).

In the Philippines, the Covid-19 crisis has affected about 27 million learners, 1 million teachers and non-teaching staff, as well as the families of learners. The Department of Education (DepEd) recently announced that classes for the next school year would begin on October 5, 2020. Classes may start earlier, but there will be no physical return to school (Obama, 2020). However, due to a problem of internet connection and lack of technological resources, majority of the students and parents prepare printed modules or modular distance learning instead of online learning. DepEd (2020) stated that printed modules or modular distance learning is a learning delivery mode where interaction takes place between the teacher and the students who are geographically remote from each other during instruction. This means lessons will be delivered outside the traditional face-to-face setup. According to Llego (2020) modular distance learning involves individualized instruction that allows learners to use self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format/electronic copy, whichever is applicable in the context of the learner, and other learning resources like Learner’s Materials, textbooks, activity sheets, study guides and other study materials. In addition, president Duterte himself has said that he won’t be allow students to go back

to school until it is safe or a vaccine becomes available, hence schools are directed to implement a learning modality where lessons will be delivered to the students in their homes (Uy, 2020).

Most earlier studies by Zaheer and Munir (2020) distance learning improves the access to education for all the aspiring students and it also overcomes the issues and concerns especially in this time of pandemic. Like conventional system, DL is also not free from certain shortcomings, for example, burden of learning is shifted on the learner (though flexibility is there), there is too much diversity in the same course, more importantly student and teacher are separated and there is a lack of guidance on the parts of the students. In addition, Au et al. (2018) noted that to enhance student persistence, teachers should be appointed for proper guidance of students for better learning.

Similarly, Tinga (2020) underlined that one of the immeasurable costs of the Covid-19 epidemic is in how children and teens have, in many respects, been pressed to “grow up.” In particular, due to the move to online and modular learning, students are increasingly taking more of an initiative in their own education and learning process. Hence, students and teachers are entering an unprecedented time of distance learning experience its own unique challenges.

1. Purpose of the Study

The main purposed of the study is to assessed the learners’ need to augment their learning performance at the identified schools in the district of Lapu-Lapu. Level of instructional support received by the learners through teacher support, school support, and technological support, academic performance of the learners and issues and concerns were considered in the main problem.

2. Research Methodology

The descriptive method of research was used in this study, which described data and the characteristics of the population under study. This method answered the questions who, what, where, when, and how. In particular, the present conditions of the respondents as regards their academic performance and interplay between the learner’s need will be described and analyzed through data gathered using the research instrument. The main questionnaire of the study will be a researcher made questionnaire due to insufficient studies in these learners need and the main respondents were teachers and learners in the identified school in Lapu-Lapu city Division.

3. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Teacher Support

Teacher Support	Teachers		Learners	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Teachers helped me develop a good study habit.	4.22	SA	3.12	MA
Communicate with my parents on weekly basis to follow up my studies.	4.44	SA	3.06	MA
Motivate me to strive hard and continue to learn independently	4.16	A	3.20	MA
Encouraged me to get good grades.	4.14	A	2.84	MA
Strict when it came to completing the module.	4.38	SA	4.14	SA
Always check to see if I had completed the task and activities in the module	4.44	SA	4.54	SA

Table 1 shows the perception of teachers and learners in terms of teachers support. Data shows that the statement refers to teachers communicate with parents on weekly basis to follow up my studies and statement refers to teachers always check to see if I had completed the task and activities in the module got the highest weighted mean of 4.44 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to teachers encourage me to get good grades got the lowest weighted mean of 4.14 which verbally described as agree. This indicates that teachers and parents should work together to effectively support the learner's wellbeing and development while on modular learning and in ensuring that the learners were doing their tasks and activities on time through constant communications and follow ups. Learners' response on the other hand, the statement refers to teachers always check to see if I had completed the task and activities in the module got the highest weighted mean of 4.54 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to teachers communicate with my parents on weekly basis to follow up my studies got the lowest weighted mean of 3.98 which verbally described as agree. This indicates that teachers and students need to communicate to each other more often to provide assistance, clarifies confusions and teachers simplifying the complex, and make abstract concepts accessible to students.

Table 2. School Support

School Support	Teachers		Learners	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Provide flexible learning modality for students	3.02	MA	3.12	MA
Physical resources	3.18	MA	3.16	MA
Mental health awareness	3.98	A	3.04	MA
Provide Safety awareness at all times	3.82	A	3.18	MA
Safety facilitation of module distributions and retrievals	3.22	A	3.10	MA
Overall, I believe my school encouragement helped me stay focused on my education.	3.04	MA	3.15	MA
Total	3.78	A	3.13	MA

Table 2 shows the perception of teachers and learners in terms of school support. Data shows that the statement refers to mental health awareness got the highest weighted mean of 3.98 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to provide flexible learning modality for students got the lowest weighted mean of 3.02 which verbally described as agree. This indicates that teachers are more concern with the mental health of the learners as much as possible the new normal set up would not add stress and depression to the students. This entail that with the flexible learning modality that the school chooses, the teachers designed activities that are good to the mental health of the students and the materials needed are locally available in their home. Learners' response on the other hand, the statement refers to policy got the highest weighted mean of 3.18 which verbally described as moderately agree, while the statement refers to mental health awareness got the lowest weighted mean of 3.04 which verbally described as agree. This indicates that policy learning from home was a challenge to both teachers and learners who were struggling in self- studies.

Table 3. Technological Support

Technological Support	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Technology makes my study easier and faster	3.84	A	3.84	A
It motivates me to explore many topics I may not have seen before.	4.16	A	4.4	SA
It helps me understand the subject material more deeply	4.48	A	4.48	A
It makes completing work in my subjects more convenient.	3.92	A	4.17	A
It allows me to collaborate with others easily, both on and outside of the home premises.	4.32	SA	4.08	A
Technology makes me feel connected to other students and my teachers	4.01	A	4.01	A
Total	4.09	A	4.15	A

Table 3 shows the perception of teachers and learners in terms of technological support. Data shows that the statement refers to It helps me understand the subject material more deeply got the highest weighted mean of 4.48 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to technology makes my study easier and faster got the lowest weighted mean of 3.84 which verbally described as agree. This indicates that technology provides the teacher varied resources, references, and samples that could help in lesson delivery or designing activities for the students. Learners' response on the other hand, the statement refers to It helps me understand the subject material more deeply got the highest weighted mean of 4.48 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to technology makes my study easier and faster got the lowest weighted mean of 4.01 which verbally described as agree. This indicates that teachers and learners were using technology to support the teaching and learning process through the use of digital learning tools that could expand their learning experiences, and provides learning materials that encourage student engagement and motivation.

Table 4. Learners Performance

Subjects	GWA	Description
Mathematics	89.25	Very Satisfactory
Science	89.49	Very Satisfactory
English	89.48	Very Satisfactory

Table 4 shows the learners performance in terms the following subjects Mathematics, Science and English. Based on the data learners got a rating of very satisfactory in all subjects. This implied that learners were able to understand their lessons during this pandemic. This indicates that teachers and learners were able to adopt the new settings of education in the new normal.

Table 5 shows the list of issues and concerns as perceived by the students group. The statement refers to most of the time I need academic supports to complete a task and activities was rated as the first rank, followed by I can't concentrate in answering the module due to unwanted sounds in our house (e.g., baby's cry, sound of music, TV, noisy neighbor), I sometimes distract when using technology such as cell phone/tablet

or laptop, when lesson is hard I either give up or study the easy parts, and lastly I am concerned that technology advances may increasingly invade my privacy.

Table 5. Issues and Concerns

ISSUES AND CONCERNS	Rank
Most of the time I need academic supports to complete a task and activities	1
When lesson is hard I either give up or study the easy parts	4
I am concerned that technology advances may increasingly invade my privacy	5
I sometimes distract when using technology such as cell phone/tablet or laptop	3
I can't concentrate in answering the module due to unwanted sounds in our house (e.g., baby's cry, sound of music, TV, noisy neighbor)	2

Conclusion

Based on the findings, our educational set-up is not excluded from the COVID-19 pandemics impact. Consistent with learning continuity plan, teachers, parents and learners have adapted to changes and take on life and improve situation with the resources made available which includes updating and assessing learner's need to augment academic performance in these times of pandemic. Results showed in teachers support, teachers and parents should work together to effectively support the learner's wellbeing and development while on modular learning and in ensuring that the learners were doing their tasks and activities on time through constant communications and follow ups. Further, the flexible learning modality that the school chooses challenged the teachers to designed activities that are good to the mental health of the students and the materials needed are locally available in their home. Results also suggest that there is a need an immediate support from the government and private sector for the development or upgrading IT infrastructure, additional cell sites for internet connection, and furthering research initiatives in every school especially during this time of pandemic.

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